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Shifting Leadership Styles in The Church

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Everyone accepts the fact that ‘effective leadership’ is a must in any organization if it must be successful and survive; and everyone accepts that the effectiveness of an organization depends on the results achieved through the practice of leadership. Everyone also accepts the fact that the criterion of leadership success is the effective performance of the leader’s group. What is not realized by many people is that there is a big difference between ‘management’ and ‘leadership’! Most of the time these two concepts are the same: and this is certainly not true!

Important work in our society is done by persons who have formal titles as President, Prime Minister, Secretary, Director, Commissioner, Administrator, etc. These may be separated by distances, life styles, duties and background, but they are all bound together by at least one commonality: they are all engaged in the practice of management. The pervasiveness of the practice of management is widely recognized. McGuire states it thus: “People who do not manage are either too young, too old, or are found in the institutions of the incompetent!”

Management, therefore, can be defined as “Allocating scarce resources to achievement of certain objectives effectively and efficiently.” Effectiveness focuses on “objective achievement”; and efficiency focuses on the “methods used to achieve the set objectives.”

The importance of management as a field is based upon the fact that modern society has developed through the creation of specialized institutions and organizations which provide the goods and services it desires. It is the managers of these institutions that allocate scarce resources to alternative and competing ends. When one studies the science of "Management", attention is focused on the nature of the Manager, the nature of Group Effort, and various forms of coordination and the manner of setting, ordering and measuring effort and goals.

Coming to the basic point of this article: is Management and Leadership, or Manager and Leader one and the same? Do these two signify the same concept? Some writers have, in the past, projected the impression that Management is a synonym of Leadership. This assumption is ill conceived! Leaders are found not only in the managerial hierarchy, but also in informal work groups. In management literature, there are several definitions of leadership. K. Young in 1946, defined leadership as one form of dominance, in which the followers willingly accept directions and control by another person. Chris Argyris, in 1976 maintained that leadership is effective influence, and to

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influence effectively, a leader requires on-the-job learning about his or her influence. Several other "management specialists" have defined the concept of leadership differently. But the common thread running through all these "definitions" is that

leadership is a process whereby one individual exerts influence over others in the achievement of an objective.

The three major views of leadership, which accept the fact that leadership is all about influencing others, place an additional qualification for leadership to be effective:

The psychological view proposes that in influencing the subordinates the leader must develop an effective motivation system; the sociological view holds that in influencing

subordinates the leader should pay attention to facilitative activity; the mutual sharing view holds that influencing is a mutual exercise. They believe that the leader has not only to influence his/her subordinates but must also be prepared to be influenced by his/her subordinates.

The ability of influencing people in the achievement of an objective is in fact true leadership, and the views expressed by scientists with different backgrounds could be considered additional benefits to a leader to be effective in influencing people in objective achievement. With this understanding of leadership, every baptized Catholic is a leader. Every baptized Catholic has an obligation, not merely by word of mouth, but by his/her life-style, based on gospel values, to influence others to recognize Jesus and love Him!

“Therefore, go and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, and teaching them to obey everything I have commanded you.” Mt. 28:19-20. Being faithful to this command of Jesus thousands of Bishops, Priests, Religious and committed lay Christians from all over the world conduct seminars, retreats and use Sunday homilies to spread the message of love and forgiveness that Jesus preached during the three years of his ministry. But the result of these efforts could be minimal. The reason for this is to be found in what Jesus Himself has said on what Christian Leadership is all about! “A new command I give you: love one another. As I have loved you, so you must love one another. By this everyone will know that you are my disciples, if you love one another.” (Jn 13: 34-35). St. Paul, in his own inimitable way, repeats the same ideas, when he says, “Set an example for those who believe, in speech, conduct, love, faith and purity, watch your life and doctrine closely. Preserve them, because if you do, you will save both yourself and your hearers” (Tim 4:12,16). What St John says in his First Epistle in 4:20, confirms what Jesus and St. Paul have said in this regard, “If anyone says, ‘I love God’, but hates his brother, he is a liar.”

Christian Leadership is all about influencing people by one’s example. The example of every baptized Christian is therefore

the best tool he/she must influence people who are searching for the truth. Dr. Albert Schweitzer, the Nobel Laureate, once said, "Example is not the main thing to influence people. It

is the only thing!" Let us continue to read the articles that appear on this subject. Let us listen carefully to the well delivered homilies. They will assist our

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responsibility to be Christian Examples and therefore Christian Leaders, but the follow-up cannot be anything else than a Christian's determination to be Christ-like in his/her behavior, so that people who encounter him/her will recognize Jesus and His teachings, by the life he/she leads, a life based on the Gospel Values of kindness, concern and love for one another.

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